

Assessment of Awareness towards Millets Amongst the College going Girls - A Regional Survey

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ABSTRACT: We all are aware of the importance of diet in our daily life. A proper diet is essential for human beings to keep them fit and healthy. For a college going girl diet plays an important role to keep them fit and active. The nutrients iron, calcium, carbohydrate etc. are essential for the growth of girls. The current year 2023 is declared as Millet year. Millets (Ragi, Kodo, Bajra, etc.) contain many nutrients which are beneficial for the girls. A survey of 135 girls students of our college and nearby college of Raipur, Chhattisgarh, India was carried out through a Google form. The objective was to know their awareness towards millets and nutrients by the analysis of compiled data. Conclusions and suggestions have been given at the end of the paper.

KEYWORDS: Balanced Diet, Human Health and Nutrients, Millet.

INTRODUCTION

Millets are whole grains that are packed with protein, antioxidants and nutrients. They may have numerous health benefits as whole grains. Each millet variety also offers a different type and amount of fiber which is good for bowel function, blood sugar and lipids. Millets like Ragi, Kodo, Bajra and Jowar are found in Chhattisgarh. For girls millets are essential to keep them fit and healthy. With the help of this survey, we would be able to know their diet problems and give proper food suggestions in order to help them to increase their interest and attitude towards millets. If essential, we can also conduct workshop to aware them about millets.

METHODOLOGY

We had asked questions for General information like name, father's name, annual income, age apart from 15 questions especially related to health, millets and food with the help of questionnaire through Google form See table 1. The questions has been filled by the girls student of government and nearby private college of Raipur.

QUESTIONS

S. No.	Question	Correct	In-Correct	Not Answered
1.	From the point of view of food this year has been declared as	15%	51%	34%
2.	Which of the following millets are mainly found in Chhattisgarh?	23%	50%	2%
3.	Which of the following millet do you use.	26%	-	-
4.	The following are the main nutrients found in millets.	73%	26%	1%
5.	Calcium and Vitamin D are essential for our body for?	95%	3%	2%
6	Do you have accurate information about a balanced diet?	65%	35%	-
7.	According to a balanced diet how many calories do you have to take in a day?	43%	47%	10%
8.	What do you eat daily to supply calcium to your body?	63%	24%	11%
9.	What do you eat on a daily basis to supply iron to your body?	62%	20%	18%
10	What do you eat daily to supply protein in your body?	70%	30%	-
11	What do you eat on a daily basis to supply carbohydrates to your body?	70%	30%	-
12	Are you or someone in your family suffering from any of the above deficiencies?			

13	How long does your hemoglobin last?	30% in range	48% less than range	12%
14	What should be the normal hemoglobin level of an adult woman?	24%	76%	-
15	Do you think you need information about millets	92% say yes		

The following report shows the analysis of compiled data collected from girls.

*In response to the question which year has this year been declared in terms of food grains, only 15% of girl students gave the correct answer, while 51% girl students gave the wrong answer and 34% did not give any answer.

*Which of the following millets are mainly found in Chhattisgarh? To this question only 23% female students gave correct answer, while 50% female students gave the correct answer to some extent and remaining 27% female students did not answer the question.

*In response to which of the following millets do you use, 50% of the girl students said Kodo, 27% said Jowar, 42% said Bajra, however 26% of the girl students responded to using more than one Millet.

*Which of the following is a nutrient found in millets? In response to this question 73% of the female students answered correctly, 26% of the female students answered incorrectly and 1% of the female students did not respond.

*In response to whether calcium and vitamin D are necessary for our body, about 95% of the female students gave the correct answer, 3% female students gave the wrong answer and 2% did not give any response.

*In response to Do you have accurate information about balanced diet, about 65% girl students gave the correct answer while 35% female students wrote that they do not have accurate information about balanced diet

*In response to how many calories you have to take in a day according to a balanced diet, 43% of the girl students gave the correct answer while 47% gave the wrong answer, 10% did not give any answer.

*In response to the eighth question, what do you eat daily for the supply of calcium in your body, 63% of the girl students wrote about milk etc., 24% of the girl students gave the wrong answer and 13% did not answer the question.

*To the question What do you eat to supply iron to your body, 62% of the female students gave the right answer while 20% of the female students gave the wrong answer and 18% did not give any response.

*In response to the question what we eat in daily life for the supply of protein, vitamin D and carbohydrates, about 70% of the female students answered correctly while 30% of the students did not answer correctly.

*In response to how much is your hemoglobin, it was observed that about 48% of the female students are having hemoglobin less than the prescribed range, only 30% of the female students were having hemoglobin within the range, while 22% were not aware about their hemoglobin hence did not give any answer.

* In response to the question of how much hemoglobin remains in an adult woman. Only 24% of the female students gave the correct information remaining students did not reply to the question.

*In response to the final question, do you think you need information about millets, 92% of female students agreed that they are very much interested to gain information about millets, balanced diet etc.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

From the analysis of the quiz/questionnaire, it can be concluded that girls students do have some knowledge about Millets, but none of the students mentioned that Millet can be source of calcium, iron, protein and carbohydrates in their body. From the assessment carried out through this questionnaire girl students are unaware about the advantages of Millets, balanced/proper diet, maintenance of vitamins like calcium, vitamin D, iron etc.

Workshops should be organized from time to time, competitions related to Millet should be held, in this way we will be able to make the girl students aware of Millets.

Google link

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/e/2PACX-1vQM3GYQYjBL6EGH-ETYEo5ChNz43RwxgcGmxhFigIJ6x7frth7sOUr5NMFjHMjXDbSUabgQNxZXjKTN/pubhtml>

Future work

Hence in order to increase the awareness about Millets, other local food and balanced diet etc., amongst the college going Girl's of Raipur district of Chhattisgarh, it is therefore proposed to carry out the work of preparing mathematical models there by suggesting a proper balanced diet at the least cost by using linear programming approach.

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